

Noyabr, 2025-Yil

TEACHING TRAINING TO DEVELOP SELF-CONFIDENCE AND ASSERTIVE
BEHAVIOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17697744>

Abstract. This study presents analytical results based on theoretical data on the formation of a person's self-confidence and the development of demanding behavior in psychological training. It also presents data from studies conducted by experienced psychologist-trainers on removing a person from a stressful situation and increasing self-confidence. In the course of our study, we discuss the advantages of using psychological methods in the development of a person's behavior in modern psychological training and the stages of conducting a psychological interview.

Keywords: Self-confidence, assertive behavior, psychological training, psychologist-trainer, psychological interview, stress.

O'ZIGA ISHONCH VA ASSERTIV XULQ-ATVORNI RIVOJLANTIRISH TRENINGI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda psixologik treninglarda shaxsning o'ziga ishonch tuyg'usini shakllantirish va assertiv xulq-atvorini rivojlantirish bo'yicha nazariy ma'lumotlarga asoslangan tahliliy natijalar keltirib o'tiladi. Shuningdek, tajribali psixolog-trenerlarning insonda stress holatidan olib chiqishda treninglar, o'ziga ishonchini orttirish bo'yicha tadqiqotlaridan olingan ma'lumotlar aytib o'tiladi. Tadqiqotimiz davomida zamonaviy psixologik treninglarda shaxsning xulq-atvorini rivojlantirishda psixologik metodlardan foydalanishning afzalliklari va psixologik suhbatlarning amalga oshirish bosqichlari haqida fikrlarni muhokama qilamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: O'ziga ishonch tuyg'usi, assertiv xulq, psixologik treninglar, psixolog-trener, psixologik suhbat, stress.

ОБУЧЕНИЕ ТРЕНИНГ РАЗВИТИЮ УВЕРЕННОСТИ В СЕБЕ И НАПОРИСТОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ

Аннотация. В настоящем исследовании представлены аналитические результаты, основанные на теоретических данных о формировании уверенности в себе и развитии асертивного поведения в психологическом тренинге. Также представлены данные исследований, проведенных опытными психологами-тренерами по тренингам вывода человека из стрессовой ситуации и повышения уверенности в себе. В ходе исследования рассматриваются преимущества использования психологических методов развития поведения в современных психологических тренингах и этапы реализации психологического интервью.

Ключевые слова: Уверенность в себе, асертивное поведение, психологический тренинг, психолог-тренер, психологическое интервью, стресс.

Introduction

In psychology, assertive behavior is considered one of the important qualities of a person necessary for the successful functioning of a person as a self-confident individual, and it plays an important role in the system of all human activities. Although personal success is associated with such qualities as goal-orientation, activity, reliability, openness, initiative and enthusiasm, a determined person embodies self-confidence, determination and perseverance, representing a model of positive behavior. Affective behavior is discussed in psychology as a quality of personality and is interpreted as an indicator of a holistic description of individual activity. In modern psychological and pedagogical research, one of the main factors determining a person's social adaptation, communicative abilities, emotional stability, and active position is self-confidence and assertive behavior. The increasing complexity of the social environment, the sharp increase in the flow of information, the increase in competition, and the psychological pressures faced by young people have further increased the need to form these qualities.

Assertive behavior is the ability of a person to defend his rights, openly express his opinion, express his inner feelings, but maintain a balanced attitude without encroaching on the rights of others. Self-confidence is a system of internal resources necessary for the socio-psychological stability of a person and effective action in the external environment. The development of self-confidence and assertive behavior is today the main guarantee of a person's psychological stability, vital activity, social communicative literacy and overall success. Scientific research shows that a person forms these skills not naturally, but through special training, exercises and social experience. Training technologies allow this process to be organized systematically, step by step and scientifically based. Psychologist-trainers help clients determine which interpersonal relationships are problematic for them and which behaviors need more attention. Additionally, therapists help clients identify beliefs and attitudes that lead to excessive passivity. Trainers take into account the specific cultural context of clients in this process. Trainers may use a combination of interviews, tests, or role-playing exercises as part of this assessment.

Therapists help clients understand what assertiveness is and how it can be helpful.

Misguided or ineffective attitudes and beliefs about assertiveness are discussed. Once clients understand the importance of assertive behavior for their situation, therapists help them develop more assertive behaviors. For example, using a technique called behavioral rehearsal, a specific situation is described and then the client and therapist take on the role of the person.

Initially, the therapist may role-play the client and model the assertive behavior. The client and therapist then switch roles and the client performs the new behavior. The therapist provides helpful, honest feedback to the client after each role-play exercise to help them improve their self-esteem or ability. Assertiveness training focuses on verbal and nonverbal behaviors. Verbal behaviors are the content of communication—what is actually said in the other person's words.

These include requests, expressions of feelings, opinions, and limitations. Nonverbal behaviors relate to communication style: eye contact, posture, tone and volume of speech, interpersonal distance, and listening.

In addition to teaching specific assertiveness skills, the therapist may work with clients to help reduce anxiety and worry through systematic desensitization, rational-emotive behavior therapy, or other techniques. As anxiety and worry decrease, people become more confident and have less anxiety or fear. We can all learn to improve our assertiveness skills. Some people can improve their assertiveness skills by reading books on assertiveness training and doing the exercises in the books. Such books are widely available in libraries and bookstores. However, for most people, professional help is needed to truly and permanently improve their assertiveness skills. This is especially true if the person's interpersonal problems are associated with intense feelings of anxiety or depression. If you or someone you know could benefit from assertiveness training, it is important to find a therapist or counselor who specializes in this approach. Ask professionals directly about their training and their experience with assertiveness training.

Learning to be assertive is like learning anything. It takes practice to learn how to do it and to build confidence in a new skill. Assertive communication involves standing up for your own rights but respecting the rights of others.

Therefore, assertive behavior directly expresses your needs and requests, while ensuring open and respectful communication. By being assertive, you are recognizing that everyone has a right to their opinion. Assertiveness allows you to feel positive about yourself when you interact with others, which increases your self-esteem. For people who are not naturally assertive, it is often possible to achieve a level of assertiveness that is completely appropriate through certain simple techniques and methods, rather than trying to adopt a more assertive personality (which can be counterproductive and stressful because it doesn't come naturally). People who are striving to be more assertive can dramatically increase their effective influence and power by engaging in just one or two of these four behaviors when faced with a more dominant or domineering personality or influence, or when faced with a situation in which they want more control, and by handling it. Here are some simple techniques and methods for developing self-confidence and a more assertive personality.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that when using modern methods in organizing psychological trainings, increasing a person's self-confidence, eliminating behavioral and psychological problems depends mainly on the psychologist-trainer. If the trainer uses psychological methods correctly, the ability to develop a person's self-confidence and show him the right path certainly depends on the experience of the psychologist-trainer. The task of the trainer, in addition to conducting psychological interviews, is to provide psychological support to depressed individuals.

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